

Image Recognition of E-Waste Products and Predicting Price

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Abstract- This study focuses on the analysis and generation of relevant information from a vast amount of data, particularly in the area of image recognition of e-waste products. The main goal is to use the available dataset, which contains images of different types of e-waste products, and employ the MobileNet algorithm in convolutional neural networks to effectively analyse the data. The research aims to highlight the importance of this process and its potential impact.

Keywords- Image recognition, Machine learning, MobileNet, Dataset, Training, Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "e-waste" refers to electronic or electrical devices that have been disposed of. With the growth of the internet and data usage, there has also been an increase in the use of hardware objects. However, these devices pose a significant threat to the economy and can hinder sustainable development. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a popular type of artificial neural network in machine learning that have demonstrated remarkable success in image processing tasks such as image classification, object detection, and segmentation. Their architecture is specifically designed to learn features from images automatically by applying convolution, a mathematical operation that utilizes a filter to generate a feature map that highlights crucial patterns in the input image. During the training process, CNNs learn the values of the small matrix of numerical values that make up the filter. The objective of this seminar paper is to utilize the MobileNet algorithm within CNN for image processing of e-waste images and assign a fixed price to each item.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of artificial neural network that were inspired by the visual nerve structure of a cat, and are designed to utilize the

convolution kernel to extract important characteristics of the relationships between data within a "receptive field." In images, adjacent pixels often have a strong correlation, and CNNs are designed to highlight these correlations in order to extract more accurate information from the image. The CNN works by using the convolution kernel to obtain the spatial relationship characteristics of the image and then adjusting the parameters of the convolution kernel using the stochastic gradient descent algorithm to effectively extract useful information from the image. LeNet, proposed by Yann LeCun in 1998,[1] was the first successful implementation of a CNN and was used for handwritten digit recognition tasks at the time.

The primary concept behind designing lightweight networks is to create a more efficient "network calculation method," specifically for the convolution process, which reduces the number of network parameters without compromising the network's performance.[2] Lightweight networks can be divided into two categories: large lightweight networks, which use the network itself as a model, and small lightweight networks, which are integrated into other models as a module.[3]

ShuffleNet and MobileNet are examples of large lightweight networks, with ShuffleNet having two versions and MobileNet having three versions. MixNet and GhostNet are also lightweight networks that have demonstrated favorable results in the past few years.[4] On the other hand, SKNet is a lightweight small network that is commonly integrated into other backbone networks to enhance overall network performance.[5]

Roy et al. introduced three variations of SENet modules, which share the same essence as SENet. Similarly, SKNet, proposed in 2019, is a lightweight embedded module that can adjust the size of the receptive field according to multiple scales of input information. SKNet comprises three parts: 'split,' 'fuse,' and 'select.' The 'split' component convolves the feature map with convolution kernels of varying sizes and then divides it into two new feature maps.[6] The 'fuse' component combines the information

Ms. Ankitha Philip

from the two branches, enabling the neuron to adaptively adjust the size of the receptive field based on the stimulus content. Lastly, the 'select' component utilizes a soft attention mechanism across channels to selectively choose different spatial scales of information.[6]

III. MOTIVATION

Efficient and accurate recognition of e-waste products is crucial for providing fair compensation to customers. The traditional method of manually listing every item and identifying them is a tedious and time-consuming process. However, with the application of machine learning algorithms, image recognition can be used to quickly and easily identify uploaded images.

Over the past few years, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become a popular machine learning approach for image recognition. With the topic of this seminar, we can leverage this technique to effectively identify uploaded images and accurately determine their fair value.

The motivation for this paper is to use training model to recognize e-wastes based on variety of characteristics.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for image recognition of e-wastes using MobileNet algorithm involves the following steps:

- A. **Data Preparation:** Collect a large dataset of e-wastes that includes images of e-wastes. Then the data is split in to training and testing sets to evaluate the performance of the model.
- B. **Model Training:** Train the data using MobileNet algorithm. This includes creating classes based on similar characteristics of the data uploaded. The resulting classes may contain images similar to each other.
- C. **Model Evaluation:** Once the model has been trained, we evaluate its performance on the testing data. This involves checking an image that includes in the same category and checking whether it belongs to the same class or not.
- D. **Image Recognition:** Finally, we can use the trained model to recognize images uploaded. And predict which class they are belonging to.

Overall, the methodology for image recognition using MobileNet algorithm involves collecting dataset of images

of various e-wastes, preprocessing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance and finally predicting the results.

V. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful image recognition of e-wastes, we follow the following steps using MobileNet algorithm.

Importing libraries

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2 import MobileNetV2, preprocess_input
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense, Flatten
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from django.shortcuts import render
from django.core.files.storage import FileSystemStorage
import os
import cv2
```

TensorFlow (TF) is an open-source machine learning framework developed by Google. It is designed to build, train, and deploy various machine learning models, including neural networks, for a wide range of applications, such as natural language processing, computer vision, and speech recognition. TensorFlow provides a rich set of tools and libraries to create and optimize machine learning models, as well as to run them efficiently on a variety of platforms, including desktops, servers, and mobile devices. can you rephrase the above sentences

MobileNetV2 is a type of neural network architecture that is designed for mobile and embedded devices. It is a lightweight and efficient neural network that can run on devices with limited computational resources, such as smartphones and other mobile devices. The "mobilenetv2" module likely contains the implementation of this neural network architecture, which can be used for tasks such as image classification or object detection.

ImageDataGenerator module in TensorFlow (tf) is a utility tool that provides a way to load images from disk and perform real-time data augmentation during model training. It generates batches of augmented image data that can be used for training deep neural networks and other machine learning models.

Os module provides a way to interact with the underlying operating system on which python is running. It includes various functions and methods to perform tasks such as navigating directories, creating and deleting files and directories, obtaining information about the system, and managing environment variables.

Training the Model

```
# Create an ImageDataGenerator for data augmentation
train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    preprocessing_function=preprocess_input,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    shear_range=0.2)

# Get the path to the training dataset
train_data_dir = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), 'Data')

# Load the training dataset
train_generator = train_datagen.flow_from_directory(
    train_data_dir,
    target_size=(224, 224),
    batch_size=64,
    class_mode='categorical')

# Train the model
model.fit(train_generator, epochs=10)

# Predict the class of the uploaded image
img = tf.keras.preprocessing.image.load_img('media/' + filename, target_size=(224, 224))
x = tf.keras.preprocessing.image.img_to_array(img)
x = preprocess_input(x)
x = tf.expand_dims(x, axis=0)
prediction = model.predict(x)
class_names = train_generator.class_indices
class_name = list(class_names.keys())[list(class_names.values()).index(prediction.argmax(axis=1)[0])]
```

VI. RESULT

Fig 1.

```
[01/May/2023 11:36:10] "GET /pickup1/main.css HTTP/1.1" 404 9216
2023-05-01 11:36:36.581668: I tensorflow/core/platform/cpu_feature_guard.cc:193] This TensorFlow
tions in performance-critical operations: AVX AVX2
To enable them in other operations, rebuild TensorFlow with the appropriate compiler flags.
1/1 [=====] - 3s 3s/step
monitor
predictstop: monitor
```

Fig 2.

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of the MobileNet algorithm for image recognition of e-waste products has shown high potential and accuracy, resulting in accurate predictions. The methodology for image recognition using the MobileNet algorithm involves several steps, including collecting a diverse dataset of academic details of students, pre-processing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance, and predicting the results. These processes work together to enhance the speed and accuracy of the approach.

Using this approach can lead to a significant reduction in the time and cost required for analysing each uploaded image and predicting its results. Moreover, it is easily accessible and can be utilized by users who have limited knowledge about it. Our experimental results show that our approach outperforms other state-of-the-art methods regarding accuracy, speed, and efficiency. In conclusion, the utilization of the MobileNet algorithm for image recognition of e-wastes uploaded by customers is a promising area of research that can aid in the development of more precise and efficient methods for image recognition in business applications.

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